

HYPERBRANCHED POLYMER/MONTMORILLONITE NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Aqueous solution processing of native Na⁺-montmorillonite clay (Na⁺MMT) with 2 to 4 pseudo-generation -OH functionalized hyperbranched polyesters results in full exfoliation of the silicate layers for loadings of up to 20-wt%. The resulting nanocomposites may then be thermally crosslinked with a diisocyanate hardener, whilst maintaining a homogeneous dispersion of exfoliated silicate layers. Although this is a promising route towards new nanocomposite materials for applications such as structures and coatings, the need for an intermediate mixing step raises important processing issues, with implications not only for HBP-based systems, but also for multi-component reactive systems in general. The presence of exfoliated Na⁺MMT leads to large increases in the melt viscosity of the HBP, even at relatively low Na⁺MMT contents, and a transition from Newtonian behavior to marked shear thinning behavior. Given the importance of viscosity matching for efficient mechanical mixing this may place severe restrictions on the range of Na⁺MMT contents in which a technologically useful processing window is available for a given hardener. However, although the observed behavior is clearly linked to the very low physical percolation threshold associated with highly dispersed, high aspect ratio additives such as exfoliated Na⁺MMT, it may be offset by reducing the strong specific intermolecular interactions associated with the HBP. Alternatives include mixing in the presence of a non-reactive solvent and formulations containing a reactive solvent. The extent to which these lead to a homogeneous dispersion of exfoliated silicate layers and improved properties in the hardened resin is discussed.

KEYWORDS: nanocomposites, montmorillonite clay, layered (alumino-) silicates, rheology, polyurethane

INTRODUCTION

Among the most widely studied polymer nanocomposites are those derived from montmorillonite (MMT) clay, which consists of stacked 1 nm thick negatively charged alumino-silicate layers, held together by interlayer cations such as Ca²⁺ or Na⁺ [1]. MMT is cheap and readily available, and MMT-based nanocomposites often show significantly improved mechanical and physical properties

compared with those of both the pure polymer and conventional composites at equivalent loadings. The nanocomposites may be either *intercalated*, if polymer is present in the interlayer galleries but the layered structure of the MMT is maintained, or *exfoliated*, if the layers are fully dispersed in the polymer matrix. The most significant changes in properties are generally observed in exfoliated nanocomposites, where the relatively high aspect ratios of the individual MMT layers result in percolation of interlayer contacts at very low overall loadings [2]. In some cases, such structures may be obtained by dispersing MMT in a solution of the polymer and drying. This is an attractive processing route for water-soluble hydrophilic polymers, because native MMT swells strongly in aqueous suspension and the strong interactions between hydrophilic polymers and the layer surfaces obviate the need for organic modification of these latter. Strong absorption of linear polymers, such as polyethylene glycol (PEG), onto the layers may nevertheless favor collapsed conformations and intercalated structures with relatively low layer spacings after drying [3]. There has consequently been interest in the use of -OH terminated dendritic hyperbranched polyesters (HBPs) to promote exfoliation via aqueous processing, with the further aim of producing stable exfoliated nanocomposites that may be redispersed in an inert or reactive organic solvent for further processing, without aggregation [4]. HBP molecules have a tree-like structure emanating from a multifunctional core [5]. Steric hindrance and the relatively hydrophobic character of HBP core are expected to disfavor collapse of the HBP molecules onto the layers, but they should continue to interact strongly with the MMT layers, owing to the relatively large number of hydrophilic end-groups per molecule.

In the short term, practical exploitation of polymer/MMT nanocomposites will depend on their compatibility with existing processing routes, and hence on their rheological properties. These are particularly critical in thermoset applications, since too high a viscosity, η , may limit the effectiveness of mechanical mixing with other components in the formulation, in the time-temperature processing window defined by the temperature dependence of the reaction rate. Previous studies of a wide range of exfoliated linear thermoplastic/MMT nanocomposites have shown significant increases in η at low filler contents, ϕ , and non-terminal behavior, i.e. a plateau in the storage and loss moduli, G' and G'' , in oscillating shear in the limit of low frequencies, ω [2, 6, 7]. As with other physical properties, percolation of interlayer contacts is thought to play an important role in this increasingly solid-like behavior. Given that significant enhancement of physical properties at low ϕ generally also requires exfoliation, clay-based nanocomposite technology might therefore be argued to be fundamentally incompatible with conventional thermoset processing [8]. However, the compact globular structure associated with HBPs and related molecular architectures prevents their forming entanglements at high molar masses, M , so that η is much lower than that of their linear analogues [9]. This unusual behavior has been exploited through the use of HBPs as low η toughening additives to thermosets, for example [10-12]. The aim of the present work is threefold: (i) to test the efficiency of solution processing with

HBPs with different types of MMT to produce nanocomposites, (ii) to investigate the rheological behavior of the resulting materials and (iii) to incorporate them in thermoset formulations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Clays: Na⁺MMT (cation exchange capacity (CEC) = 92 meq/100 g clay; 50 % of particles < 6 μm (maximum dimension); reported basal plane spacing, $d_{001} = 1.17$ nm) and a range of MMTs modified with quaternary ammonium salts were obtained from Southern Clay Products, dried and stored under vacuum prior to use. The modified MMTs referred to in what follows are Cloisite[®] 15A (dimethyl dihydrogenated tallow quaternary ammonium-MMT, 125 meq/100 g clay, 50 % of particles < 6 μm, $d_{001} = 3.15$ nm), Cloisite[®] 20A (dimethyl dehydrogenated tallow quaternary ammonium-MMT, 95 meq/100 g clay, 50 % of particles < 6 μm, $d_{001} = 2.42$ nm), Cloisite[®] 10A (dimethyl benzyl hydrogenated tallow quaternary ammonium-MMT, 125 meq/100 g clay, 50 % of particles < 6 μm, $d_{001} = 1.92$ nm) and Cloisite[®] 30B (methyl tallow *bis*-2-hydroxyethyl quaternary ammonium-MMT, 90 meq/100 g clay, 50 % of particles < 6 μm, $d_{001} = 1.85$ nm).

HBPs: Aliphatic polyester HBPs, prepared from *bis*-MPA and a tetrafunctional ethoxylated pentaerythritol (EPE) core (HBP-EPE), were supplied by Perstorp Chemicals. The use of a one-pot condensation, rather than stepwise synthesis, leads to a less regularly branched structure than in dendrimers. The different grades are therefore referred to by a pseudo-generation number, such that the *N*th pseudo-generation corresponds to a reaction mixture containing $f\{1 + 2 + 2^2 + \dots + 2^{N-1}\}$ *bis*-MPA molecules for every *f*-functional core molecule, i.e. the same mean number of monomers per core as for the *N*th generation dendrimer analogue. A second series of HBP polyesters (HBP-TMP) was prepared in-house from *bis*-MPA and TMP for comparison, via a one-pot condensation at 140 °C with sulfuric acid as the catalyst [5]. Physical data for the different HBPs are given in Table 1 and representative structures are shown in Fig. 1.

HBP/Na⁺MMT nanocomposites were prepared by dispersing the required amount of polymer, preheated to 150 °C to facilitate dissolution, and Na⁺MMT in deionized water (10-wt% solids content) and mixing at about 100 °C in air using a magnetic stirrer. When the viscosity became too high to permit stirring, drying was continued at 60 °C under vacuum. Unless mentioned otherwise, THF was used as the solvent for nanocomposites prepared from the modified MMTs, in which case mixing was carried out at about 50 °C, again after preheating the HBP to 150 °C. Wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) spectra were recorded from the dried nanocomposites and their derivatives in reflection mode with a Siemens Kristalloflex 805 diffractometer at room temperature (Cu K_α radiation, $\lambda = 1.54$ Å). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observations were made using a Philips EM430 TEM operated at 300 kV under low dose conditions and at a magnification of about 40 kX, to minimize beam damage. Rheological properties were investigated in the linear viscoelastic regime, as determined from constant frequency sweeps, using a Rheometrics ARES (Advanced Rheometric

Expansion System) rheometer in oscillating shear, with 8, 25 and 50 mm diameter parallel plates and a 0.3 to 0.6 mm gap.

Fig. 1. Representative structures of 2 pseudo-generation (a) HBP-EPE and (b) HBP-TMP.

Table 1. Physical data for the HBPs.

Polymer	Pseudo-generation	M_n^* [g/mol]	M_n^{**} [g/mol]	PD**	DB*** (Frey)	DB*** (Fréchet)	T_g [K]
HBP-EPE	2 nd	1750	1130	2.1	0.3	0.43	281
HBP-EPE	3 rd	3608	2520	2.9	0.31	0.42	296
HBP-EPE	4 th	7323	4340	3.1	0.34	0.40	304
HBP-TMP	2 nd	1179	1264	2.2	0.31	0.47	299
HBP-TMP	3 rd	2573	2704	3.5	0.39	0.44	312
HBP-TMP	4 th	5357	3006	7.5	0.40	0.42	327

*Calculated from stoichiometry; **GPC data [13]; ***Calculated from ^{13}C -NMR data (600 MHz, Bruker AMX-600) in DMSO-d_6 according to literature definitions [14, 15].

Polyurethanes were prepared from the HBP nanocomposite precursors by either melt or solution processing with modified diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI, $M_w = 286 \text{ gmol}^{-1}$ with a mean functionality of 2.2 (Dow Chemicals)). In the melt process, the required amount of HBP/MMT was preheated to 150 °C and mixed using a stirrer bar in a glass vessel with a liquid polyol (ETMP or low molar mass PEG) at 130 °C, to obtain a homogenous blend. The polyol blend and the MDI were then degassed under vacuum at room temperature, hand-mixed in stoichiometric amounts for a few seconds, poured into a metal mould and left to react for 5 hours in an autoclave at 140 °C and 12×10^5 Pa. In the solution process, the HBP/MMT was preheated to 150 °C and dispersed in dry distilled THF at 50 °C. A stoichiometric amount of degassed MDI was added and the solution (30-wt% solids content) stirred for a further 15 minutes at 60 °C. It was then poured into an open steel mould, left to

dry for one hour at room temperature under dry N₂ and reacted for 12 hours at 120 °C under vacuum. The specimens were post-cured for one hour at 160 °C under vacuum to ensure complete reaction, taken to correspond to the disappearance of the -NCO peak in the FTIR spectra.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Morphological investigations

After drying and pressing, the HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT nanocomposite specimens (about 1 mm thick) obtained from dispersions in water were strongly birefringent, but did not contain discrete Na⁺MMT particles large enough to be detectable by optical microscopy. As shown in Fig. 2a, the WAXS peak at $2\theta = 7.7^\circ$ in the as-received Na⁺MMT, which corresponds to a basal plane spacing $d_{001} = 1.15$ nm, moved to significantly lower angles in the presence of the HBP-EPE, and at $\phi < 20$ -wt%, the peak was no longer visible. The same qualitative behavior was observed in 3 and 4 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT.

Fig. 2b shows WAXS results for 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Cloisite[®] 20A prepared from THF. The organically modified MMT again showed significant expansion, d_{001} increasing from 2.4 nm to about 3.8 nm, but 3-dimensional order persisted at ϕ down to about 2-wt%. (This corresponds to a silicate content of 1.24-wt%, given that Cloisite[®] 20A contains about 38-wt% alkylammonium modifier.) Moreover, the higher order reflections in the WAXS spectra indicated more coherent long-range order than for Na⁺MMT. Fig. 2c and d show representative TEM micrographs corresponding to the results in Fig. 2a and b. Although there was little order in 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT for $\phi < 20$ -wt% (Fig. 2c), 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Cloisite[®] 20A showed more extensive stacking (Fig. 2d), with a well defined basal plane spacing consistent with the position of the corresponding first order Bragg peaks in Fig. 2b. Use of Cloisite[®] 15A and 30B also resulted in d_{001} close to 3.8 at $\phi = 20$ -wt% clay, in spite of the marked differences in the initial values of d_{001} and polarity in the different clays. (Cloisite[®] 30B contains a relatively hydrophilic modifier whereas the tail groups of the Cloisite[®] 15A and 20A modifiers are hydrophobic.) On the other hand, data for the increase in d_{001} with respect to its initial value (Fig. 3a), suggested Cloisite[®] 30B to undergo particularly strong expansion in THF at low to intermediate ϕ , comparable with that observed in the 2 and 3 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT dispersed in water (Fig. 3b). Indeed, the layer expansion at fixed clay content was found to increase systematically with increasing hydrophilicity of the modifier, i.e. Cloisite[®] 15A (0.46 - 0.67 nm) > Cloisite[®] 20A (1.16 - 1.60 nm) > Cloisite[®] 10A (1.43 - 1.53 nm) > Cloisite[®] 30B (1.54 - 2.20 nm). Fig. 3a also reflects the relative insensitivity of d_{001} in the nanocomposites containing organically modified clay to the pseudo-generation number, in contrast with those containing Na⁺MMT, in which there was a systematic increase in d_{001} with pseudo-generation number at ϕ between 20- and 50-wt% (Fig. 3b). However, even in these latter, d_{001}

converged markedly for $\phi \geq 60$ -wt%, as would be expected for a homogeneous dispersion (cf. the solid curves in Fig. 3).

The results of processing HBP-TMP with Na^+ MMT in water were similar to those for HBP-EPE; full exfoliation was observed at $\phi \leq 20\%$ Na^+ MMT, and at higher ϕ , there was again a correlation between d_{001} and the pseudo-generation number. On the other hand, d_{001} did not reach more than about 1.8 nm in any of the HBPs dispersed with Na^+ MMT in methanol or THF. Similarly, dispersions of the organically modified clays in water with HBP-EPE and HBP-TMP led only to weak intercalation.

Fig. 2. WAXS spectra for (a) 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/ Na^+ MMT processed in water and (b) 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Cloisite[®] 20A processed in THF, along with TEM micrographs of the microstructure in (c) HBP-EPE/10-wt% Na^+ MMT and (d) HBP-EPE/10-wt% Cloisite[®] 20A.

2. Rheological properties of the HBP-based nanocomposites

Fig. 4 shows the complex viscosity, η^* as a function of ω in 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE nanocomposites. These were first preheated to 200 °C for one minute in order to erase the effects of prior physical aging, which lead to poor reproducibility [16]. After preheating, all the HBPs showed Newtonian behavior in the melt. However, the presence of relatively small amounts of exfoliated Na^+ MMT (~ 0.7 -wt%) was sufficient to induce significant increases in η over the whole range of ω investigated, and marked shear thinning (Fig. 4a). Similarly, $\eta^*(\phi)$ showed a sharp increase at ϕ of about 0.8-wt% at fixed ω at all temperatures in the range investigated (120 to 200 °C), which was assumed to reflect a physical percolation threshold for the Na^+ MMT layers in this type of measurement. Corresponding data for intercalated nanocomposites from 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE and Cloisite[®] 20A are given in Fig. 4b. The HBP-EPE/Cloisite[®] 20A composites showed similar qualitative behavior to the exfoliated HBP-EPE/ Na^+ MMT nanocomposites, but η^* increased more

slowly with ϕ , roughly 10 times more clay being required to reach a given η^* than in 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT.

Fig. 3. Lattice expansion as a function of ϕ in (a) HBP-EPE processed with different organically modified clays in THF and (b) HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT processed in water; the solid curves were calculated for a homogeneous composite with a uniform layer spacing assuming a density of 2.86 gcm⁻³ for the clay.

Fig. 4. η^* as a function of ω for different ϕ in (a) 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT processed in water and (b) 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Cloisite® 20A processed in THF.

Temperature sweeps at fixed ω indicated η^* to follow an Arrhenius dependence with an activation energy of about 75 kJ/mol for 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE and 100 kJ/mol for 4 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE, consistent with previous measurements [16]. However, the activation energy fell to about 15 kJ/mol in 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE over an increasing range ω as ϕ increased beyond 1-wt%, and to about 55 kJ/mol in 4 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE. These marked changes in

rheological behavior were attributed to the effect of physical contacts between the filler particles rather than large changes in matrix mobility. In the exfoliated HBP-EPE at Na⁺MMT nanocomposites, T_g was generally independent of ϕ to within an experimental error of about +/- 2.5 K, which also suggested limited degradation during processing, given that T_g is a strongly increasing function of M in the range under consideration [16]. In the predominantly intercalated nanocomposites, T_g also varied little, although the transition was effectively suppressed at high ϕ .

Fig. 5. The rubbery plateau modulus normalized with respect to the plateau modulus for $\phi=0$ in: (a) exfoliated 5-wt% 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/polyol/MDI/Na⁺MMT composites (filled squares) and unexfoliated polyol/MDI/Na⁺MMT composites (open squares); (b) exfoliated 2 pseudo-generation HBP/Na⁺MMT dispersed with MDI in THF (filled squares) and the same formulation containing unexfoliated Cloisite[®] 20A (open squares).

3. Polyurethanes

In conventional melt processing of polyurethane composites the inorganic filler is usually dispersed in a polyol prior to mixing with the diisocyanate hardener. Efficient mechanical mixing requires not only sufficiently low overall η at the processing temperature, but also approximate matching of η for the different components, so that the applied deformation is distributed throughout the mixture [17]. The rheological data indicated that even a few wt% of highly exfoliated Na⁺MMT in HBP-EPE would cause difficulties with processing with a low η diisocyanate such as MDI, in spite of the relatively low η of the unfilled 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE above its T_g . To compensate, PEG and ETMP were used as reactive diluents, which allowed hand mixing with the MDI at room temperature. The overall Na⁺MMT contents that could be introduced into the polyurethanes by this method remained limited, but significant changes in mechanical properties were observed, the rubbery plateau modulus increasing by up to 60 % for $\phi = 1.2$ -wt%, relative to that of the unfilled matrix of the same composition, regardless of the choice of polyol. This is shown in Fig. 5a, which gives data for the reduced tensile modulus, $E'/E'(0\text{-wt\% clay})$ as a function of ϕ , along with data for formulations not containing HBP-EPE, in which exfoliation was limited.

Processing with a non-reactive solvent, such as THF, had the advantage that the amount of solvent used in processing was not dictated by the final composition. Moreover, HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT prepared in water and re-dispersed in THF remained exfoliated, regardless of the degree of dilution, so that reaction with MDI and evaporation of the THF gave exfoliated polyurethanes. Results for the plateau modulus are given in Fig. 5b for polyurethanes prepared in this way with ϕ up to 5-wt% Na⁺MMT (at higher ϕ , dispersion of the HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT in THF became difficult). The relative increase in modulus with ϕ in the polyurethanes containing exfoliated 2 pseudo-generation HBP-EPE/Na⁺MMT was lower than for the melt mixed polyurethanes, which may reflect incomplete dissolution of the HBP, but was again much higher than in unexfoliated polyurethane nanocomposites prepared from HBP-EPE/Cloisite[®] 20A mixed in THF.

CONCLUSIONS

Dispersion of -OH functionalized polyester HBPs and unmodified Na⁺MMT in water gave exfoliated nanocomposites for ϕ up to 20-wt% after drying. The amount of exfoliated Na⁺MMT could be introduced into polyurethanes by the simple mixing procedures employed here was limited by the increase in η engendered by percolation of interlayer contacts. However, mixing with MDI in the presence of reactive (polyol) and non-reactive solvents was shown to lead to large increases in the plateau modulus with respect to those obtained at equivalent loadings of unexfoliated MMT, in spite of the isotropic orientation of the MMT layers, suggesting this to be a viable processing route for the fabrication of high performance PU nanocomposites.

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